

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram of Study Selection.

The PRISMA 2020-based diagram illustrates the flow of studies through the systematic review process. Out of 7,842 records initially identified, 312 duplicates were removed, leaving 7,530 records for screening. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, 52 articles were included in the final review.

Figure 2: Distribution of Retrieved Articles across Databases.

Bar chart showing the number of retrieved studies per database (2010-2024). IEEE Xplore and Scopus contributed the highest number of articles, confirming their dominance in wireless communication research.

Figure 3: Number of Publications per Year (2010-2024)

Yearly publication trend for RL-based NOMA power allocation. The figure shows steady growth after 2016, with a peak between 2021-2023.

Figure 4: Publications per Outlet (Journal vs. Conference)

Distribution of included studies by type of outlet. Journals accounted for 71.2% (37 studies), while conferences contributed 28.8% (15 studies).

Figure 5: Distribution of Journal Publishers (2010-2024)

Bar chart showing the share of included publications by publisher. IEEE Xplore led with 20 (38.5%) publications, followed by Scopus (15), Web of Science (10), SpringerLink (5), and Wiley (2).

Figure 6: Research Issues versus Future Directions in AI-driven RL for 6G Networks. Conceptual diagram mapping current unresolved issues (scalability, imperfect CSI, fairness, energy efficiency) to future research directions (multi-agent RL, transfer learning, energy-aware frameworks, explainability)